

**ANALYSIS OF TECHNOLOGY AND METHODS OF USING MIXED
EDUCATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH****Yusupova Nargiza Nigmatovna**

Tashkent state Uzbek language and literature

University "English language"

Department's teacher Ph.D.

Yusupova_n@navoiy-uni.uznargizanigmatovna@gmail.com

tel: 998977702744

Abstract. This article describes how to use and apply modern and mixed educational technologies in the process of mixed education. Information and communication technologies are designed to ensure the cognitive activity of students and introduce interactive forms of lessons, the most effective of which is currently mixed education. Blended education in the higher education system means the integration of distance education technology (online), full-time education (working with a teacher) and Internet education. Such a model allows you to control the time, place, speed and method of studying the educational material. Mixed education allows combining traditional methods and modern information and communication technologies in teaching academic subjects.

Keywords. Globalization of the information system, Organization and management of educational process, Distance education, blended learning.

In the conditions of integration into the world community and globalization of socio-cultural processes, the rapid development of information and communication technologies is increasing the need to learn foreign languages as a means of mutual communication. In this regard, the international information exchange system, individualization and differentiation of education in higher education institutions,

methods of effective use of digital technologies in the development of communicative competence of students in the process of teaching English, development of criteria for measuring the level of development of speech skills, their modern ensuring compliance with educational requirements is becoming more and more important. Globalization of the information system on a global scale has led to the increase in the effectiveness of socio-cultural strategies in the world's leading educational institutions, and the development of professional and socio-cultural competence of foreign language specialists, and the use of information and communication technologies. Competent approach to improving the knowledge, skills and abilities of future specialists in foreign languages and applying the latest achievements of science and technology to the educational process, introducing advanced methods of teaching in the environment of information and communication technologies in the world experience. from the point of view, there was a need to scientifically improve technologies that diagnose the level of development of foreign language skills in students.

Organization and management of educational process informatization in our republic, effective use of information technologies in the processes of offline and online teaching of subjects, carrying out scientific and research work on issues of competence of future specialists in foreign languages are of great practical importance. going to be. In particular, in the program for the comprehensive development of the higher education system in Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, developed in cooperation with the UN UNESCO Committee and DGP Research & Consulting priority tasks such as "implementation" are defined.

Decision No. 355 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2013 on the use of modern information and telecommunication tools in the educational process "On measures to introduce a system for assessing the state of development of information and communication technologies in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted, and in order to implement this decision, attention has been paid to connecting educational institutions in our republic to the Internet and providing

them with electronic communications. In addition, a number of tasks have been defined in the decisions related to the establishment of a public educational information network in our republic, the creation of the National Information System, and the creation of the necessary conditions for comprehensively meeting the information needs of all educational institutions.

All this is the introduction of new pedagogical and information and communication technologies, including distance education, electronic forums, video conferences, creation of electronic textbooks and training manuals, and their use in the educational process. are activities aimed at In general, the emergence and improvement of information and communication and computer technologies is related to the needs of society for fast and error-free transmission, processing, and storage of information, as well as more reasonable and correct decisions for the specialist. allows to adapt in time to the conditions of real reality in the environment.

Distance education is becoming an urgent issue not only in foreign countries, but also in the education system of our country. Today, it is increasingly used in almost all educational institutions.

A number of research works have been conducted on the problems of distance education implementation in the educational system. In particular, regarding the problems of teaching on the basis of distance education in our republic, scientific research by A.A. -research works have been carried out.

Distance education models and their classes, as well as possibilities of using distance education in professional development, were studied in A.A. Abdukadirov's scientific research.

In the research work of N.A. Muslimov, the organizational and methodical principles of the creation of the educational-methodical complex of distance education and the requirements for the creation of electronic textbooks were developed. It is also justified that distance education is an innovative technology of mutual, appropriate interactive communication between subjects of education and educational tools. In the

research work, it has been proven that it is possible to effectively use the types of education organized on the basis of correspondence education, radio and television education, network education, mobile technology and case technology in the practical organization of distance education.

The didactic and psychophysiological aspects of the development and application of electronic teaching-methodical materials are reflected in the works of R.R. Boqiyev.

In the research work of D. M. Saifurov, a hypothetical model of the professional qualities of a teacher-tutor was created based on the model of the information-educational environment that provides distance learning. In the research, the criteria for evaluating the motivational, cognitive-practical, and emotional training of teachers working in the distance education system were developed.

Currently, the creation of various software tools and methods of using distance education ensures the rapid development of this education. In particular, S. Qasimov, Sh. Nazirov, Kh. Bulakbayev, R. Usmanov, F. Kholikov have conducted scientific research on the application of effective technologies of distance learning-based teaching in the field of education.

Organizational and pedagogical problems of distance education based on Internet technology abroad are reflected in the works of A. Amadco, A. Dodds, M. Moore, G. Kearsley and others.

A. Amadco's scientific research focused on the nature of student interaction with the educational process and the formation of requirements for teaching tools.

M.Moore and G.Kearsley's scientific research focused mainly on the importance and essence of distance education, while A.Doods focused on the systems, tools, and pedagogical elements of distance education that are different from traditional education. conducted scientific research on forms.

Russian scientists and specialists in the theory and practice of distance education, including A.A. Andreyev, A.I. Bashmakov, N.V. Monakhov, V.I. Ovsyannikov, Ye.S.

Polat, M.V. Moiseyeva, V.P. Tikhomirov, A.N. Tikhonov, A.D. Ivannikov, and others, have carried out effective research they took

A.A. Andreyev's scientific research work sheds light on the scientific-theoretical foundations of distance education, defined methods, forms and tools. In the research work, the content and capabilities of distance learning case technology, correspondence education, radio and television model, network learning and mobile technology models are compared and the factors influencing the quality of distance learning are identified.

Depending on the knowledge needs, interests and abilities of students, the variety and variety of teaching content, organizational forms, and methods are important at all stages of education, especially for future specialists, including , is very relevant at the stage of professional-pedagogical training of future teachers. It is for this reason that a necessary condition for achieving a modern new quality of education is the introduction of new forms of teaching in higher education institutions, the formation of a flexible system of teaching, and the provision of continuous education. As we mentioned above, distance education has been an alternative to traditional education for several years.

Another important advantage of a flexible curriculum for blended learning is that students have immediate access to help when they encounter problems or errors. The program immediately reports the error and offers additional training material on the same issue. The teacher will have a set of data that will allow him to analyze the most common mistakes and problems, and thereby make corrections to the teaching system. Knowledge level indicators help to group students according to knowledge levels to provide additional explanation of the learning material or to give practical tasks.

Mixed educational conditions place high demands on the level of professional skills of teachers. Such a model of teaching changes the work of the teacher that is, taking him from the traditional teaching process and administrative tasks to working with databases and providing individual help and support to students. The tasks of the teacher extend from planning the lesson and providing information on the studied topic

to solving the problem of motivating, stimulating and facilitating the learning process. This requires the teacher to constantly acquire independent knowledge and regularly expand his knowledge. Its tasks include assessment, analysis and data collection; use of databases for individual students, groups and the entire audience as an integral part of the planning process; including the use of standardized tests and other assessment options to guide the work of students of varying readiness and achievement.

In the mixed education system, the teacher's leadership skills are extremely important. In order to help the students to get used to the new environment, the teacher should model and demonstrate the learning process to the students, how to find the necessary information or answers to the given questions, and also teach the students to ask the right questions. . A teacher must know how to manage the different types of learning activities needed to complete a specific assignment or project. In the blended learning model, the teacher does not simply deliver the information taught to the students, but helps them to form the skills of applying and adapting the existing information to new conditions and situations. The task of the teacher is to correctly interpret and analyze the data, and the task of the students is to determine the cause-and-effect relationships, combine the collected data and demonstrate the knowledge gained by applying them to specific situations.

Therefore, the mixed education model requires continuous professional development and improvement from the teacher. This is due to its effective modification of existing strategies to teach students to study independently and freely, acquire knowledge and skills. Modern technology can provide the teacher with the information necessary to understand the individual needs of students. The analysis of these data allows the teacher to develop the necessary program to support and deepen the knowledge acquired by students.

The essence of the educational process is the delivery of educational information by the teacher to the student. Thus, in general, any technology used in pedagogy or in the educational process has an informational character. In most cases, the concept of

"information technology" is used for all technologies created for use in computer equipment and telecommunications. In order to avoid misinterpretation, it is necessary to clarify the content of three important concepts in distance education. These are "educational information", "educational technologies" and "information technologies". Now let's talk about each of these three concepts.

Educational information (information) is necessary for the competent implementation of this or that activity by the learner.

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